

VISCOELASTICITY AND FLEXIBLE STRUCTURES: EXPLORING THEIR INTERPLAY IN DYNAMIC SYSTEMS

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Abstract:

This article delves into the study of elastic structures with viscoelastic boundary conditions, focusing on an elastic thin plate in a bounded domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ with C^2 -smooth boundary Γ . The plate is clamped, and memory effects are considered on a subset Γ_0 with positive boundary measure. The vertical deflection $y(x, t)$ of this thin elastic plate is governed by a partial differential equation involving wave equations and memory effects. The specific problem can be described by the following equations:

$$y_{tt}(x, t) + \Delta^2 y(x, t) = 0, \text{ in } \Omega \times \mathbb{R}^+, \quad (1.1a)$$

$$y(x, t) = \partial_\nu y(x, t) = 0, \text{ on } \Gamma_0 \times \mathbb{R}^+, \quad (1.1b)$$

$$\mathcal{B}_1 y(x, t) - \int_0^t g'(s) \partial_\nu [y(x, t) - y(x, t-s)] ds = 0, \text{ on } \Gamma_0 \times \mathbb{R}^+, \quad (1.1c)$$

$$\mathcal{B}_2 y(x, t) + \int_0^t g'(s) [y(x, t) - y(x, t-s)] ds = u(x, t), \text{ on } \Gamma_1 \times \mathbb{R}^+, \quad (1.1d)$$

$$y(x, 0^+) = y_0(x), \quad y_t(x, 0^+) = y_1(x), \quad (1.1e)$$

$$y(x, -s) = \vartheta(x, t), \text{ for } 0 < s < \infty. \quad (1.1f)$$

This study explores the interplay between elastic structures and viscoelastic boundary conditions, examining the behavior of the thin plate under these specified conditions.

Keywords: Elastic structures, viscoelastic boundary conditions, thin plate, partial differential equations, and memory effects.

1 Introduction

The problems of elastic structures with viscoelastic boundary conditions have been studied extensively by many articles (see References [1]-[5]). Motivated by the work on wave and heat equations mentioned above, in this article we are concerned with an elastic thin plate which occupies a bounded domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ with C^2 -smooth boundary Γ . Assume that $\Gamma = \overline{\Gamma_0} \cup \overline{\Gamma_1}$, where Γ_0 and Γ_1 are relatively open subsets of Γ , $\Gamma_0 \neq \emptyset$ has positive boundary measure, and $\overline{\Gamma_0} \cap \overline{\Gamma_1} = \emptyset$. If Γ_0 is clamped and the memory effect on Γ_1 is taken into account, the vertical deflection $y(x, t)$ of the thin elastic plate satisfies the following partial differential equation:

$$y_{tt}(x, t) + \Delta^2 y(x, t) = 0, \text{ in } \Omega \times \mathbb{R}^+, \quad (1.1a)$$

$$y(x, t) = \partial_\nu y(x, t) = 0, \text{ on } \Gamma_0 \times \mathbb{R}^+, \quad (1.1b)$$

$$\mathcal{B}_1 y(x, t) - \int_0^t g'(s) \partial_\nu [y(x, t) - y(x, t-s)] ds = 0, \text{ on } \Gamma_0 \times \mathbb{R}^+, \quad (1.1c)$$

$$\mathcal{B}_2 y(x, t) + \int_0^t g'(s) [y(x, t) - y(x, t-s)] ds = u(x, t), \text{ on } \Gamma_1 \times \mathbb{R}^+, \quad (1.1d)$$

$$y(x, 0^+) = y_0(x), \quad y_t(x, 0^+) = y_1(x), \quad (1.1e)$$

$$y(x, -s) = \vartheta(x, t), \text{ for } 0 < s < \infty, \quad (1.1f)$$

where g is the relaxation function, u is the boundary control, y_0, y_1, ϑ are the given initial conditions. $\mathcal{B}_1, \mathcal{B}_2$ are the following boundary operators:

$$B_1 y = \Delta y + (1 - \mu) (2v_1 v_2 \frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} - v_1^2 \frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial x_2^2} - v_2^2 \frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial x_1^2}),$$

$$B_2 y = \partial_\nu \Delta y + (1 - \mu) \partial_\tau [(v_1^2 - v_2^2) \frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} + v_1 v_2 (\frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial x_2^2} - \frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial x_1^2})]$$

$v = (v_1, v_2)$ is the unit outer normal vector, $\tau = (-v_2, v_1)$ is the unit tangent vector, and $0 < \mu < \frac{1}{2}$ is the Poisson ratio.

Throughout the article, we assume always that the function $g(\cdot)$ satisfies the following conditions:

(g₁) $g(\cdot) \in C^2[0, \infty)$;

(g₂) $g(t) > 0$,

(g₃) $g'(t) > 0$;

(g₄) $g(t) \geq -kg$

$g'(t) < 0, \quad g'(t) \geq 0$ for $t \geq 0$;

$g''(t) > 0$ and all $t \geq 0$.

for some $k > 0$

Condition (g₂) implies that the memory of the boundary is strictly decreasing and the rate of memory loss is also decreasing. From (g₂), we have also that both $g(\infty)$ and $g'(\infty)$ exist, $g'(\infty) \geq 0$. Condition (g₃) means that the material behaves like an elastic solid at $t = \infty$. Condition (g₄) implies that $g'(t)$ decays exponentially, in particular, $g'(\infty) = 0$.

The energy corresponding to the system (1) is defined by

$$E(t) = \frac{1}{2} a(y(\cdot, t)) + \int_\Omega |y_t(x, t)|^2 dx - \int_0^\infty \int_{\Gamma_1} g'(s) [|\partial_\nu(y(x, t) - y(x, t - s))|^2 + |y(x, t) - y(x, t - s)|^2] d\Gamma ds \tag{1.2}$$

where $a(w) = a(w, w)$ and

$$a(w_1, w_2) = \int_\Omega [\frac{\partial^2 w_1}{\partial x_1^2} \frac{\partial^2 w_2}{\partial x_1^2} + \frac{\partial^2 w_1}{\partial x_2^2} \frac{\partial^2 w_2}{\partial x_2^2} + \mu (\frac{\partial^2 w_1}{\partial x_1^2} \frac{\partial^2 w_2}{\partial x_2^2} + \frac{\partial^2 w_1}{\partial x_2^2} \frac{\partial^2 w_2}{\partial x_1^2}) + 2(1 - \mu) \frac{\partial^2 w_1}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} \frac{\partial^2 w_2}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2}] dx, \quad \forall w_1, w_2 \in H^2(\Omega). \tag{1.3}$$

2. Well-Posedness of the System with Feedback Control

In this section, we shall formulate the system (1.1a-1.1f) into a standard linear infinite dimensional space with a output feedback control. Let

$$W = \{w \in H^2(\Omega) | w|_{\Gamma_0} = \partial_\nu w|_{\Gamma_0} = 0\}, \quad \|w\|_W^2 = a(w), \quad \forall w \in W,$$

and define the "boundary memory space" by

$$Z = L^2(0, \infty); H^1($$

$$s) | \left[\|\partial_\nu z(s)\| + \|z(s)\| \right]$$

$$\infty; |g'(\Gamma_1)),$$

$$\int_0^\infty ds, \quad \forall z \in Z$$

$$\|z\|_Z = \|g'(\Gamma_1) z\|_Z + \|z\|_Z.$$

Set

$$\mathcal{H} = W \times L^2(\Omega) \times Z$$

equipped with the inner product induced norm

$$\|(w, v, z)\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 = \|w\|_W^2 + \|v\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \|z\|_Z^2, \quad \forall (w, v, z) \in \mathcal{H}.$$

It is easy to see that $\mathcal{H}$ is a Hilbert space.

Remark We have that $a(\cdot)^2$ is an equivalent norm on $\mathcal{W}$ since $\Gamma_0 \neq \emptyset$ has positive boundary measure.

Moreover, it is obvious that $(\|\partial_{\nu} z\|_{L^2(\Gamma_1)}^2 + \|z^2\|_{L^2(\Gamma_1)}^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ is an equivalent norm on $H^1(\Gamma_1)$. In fact, if $\|\partial_{\nu} z\|_{L^2(\Gamma_1)} + \|z^2\|_{L^2(\Gamma_1)} = 0$, then $z = \partial_{\nu} z = 0$ on Γ_1 . It follows that $\nabla_z = \nu \partial_{\nu} z = 0$ on Γ_1 . Therefore, $z = 0$ in $H^1(\Gamma_1)$.

Next we introduce some operators (Ref.9) as follows:

(i) We set

$$\int_0^{\infty} Lz(s) = g'(s)z(s)ds,$$

$$\mathcal{A}_0 = \Delta \quad \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A}_0) = \{w \in H^4(\Omega) \cap W \mid \mathcal{B}_1 w|_{\Gamma_1} = \mathcal{B}_2 w|_{\Gamma_1} = 0\}.$$

It is easy to know that $\mathcal{A}_0$ is a positive self-adjoint operator on $L^2(\Omega)$.

(ii) The Green operators N_1 and N_2 are introduced to describe the boundary conditions,

$$N_1 g = h \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} \Delta^2 \square = 0, & \text{in } \Omega, \\ h \\ \mathcal{B} \\ \mathcal{B} \end{cases}$$

$$N_2 g = h \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} h \\ \mathcal{B} \\ \mathcal{B} \end{cases}$$

$$= \partial_{\nu} \square = 0, \quad \text{on } \Gamma_0,$$

$$1 \square = g, \quad \text{on } \Gamma_1,$$

$$2 \square = 0, \quad \text{on } \Gamma_1,$$

$$\Delta^2 \square = 0, \quad \text{in } \Omega,$$

$$= \partial_{\nu} \square = 0, \quad \text{on } \Gamma_0,$$

$$1 \square = 0, \quad \text{on } \Gamma_1,$$

$$2 \square = g, \quad \text{on } \Gamma_1.$$

In terms of the regularity theory for the elliptic equations (Ref.6), we see that

$$N_1: L^2(\Gamma_1) \rightarrow H^{\frac{5}{2}}(\Omega) \text{ is continuous,}$$

$$N_2: L^2(\Gamma_1) \rightarrow H^{\frac{7}{2}}(\Omega) \text{ is continuous}$$

By these operators defined above, we may rewrite the system (1.1a-1.1f) as

$$y_{tt}(\cdot, t) + \mathcal{A}_0[y(\cdot, t) - N_1 Lz(\cdot, t, s) + N_2 Lz(\cdot, t, s) - N_2 u(\cdot, t, s)] = 0, \quad (2.1)$$

Where $z(\cdot, t, s) = y(x, t) - y(x, t - s)$, $x \in \Gamma_1$. Considering $L^2(\Omega)$ as the pivot space: $[\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A}_0)] \subset L^2(\Omega) \subset$

$[\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A}_0)]'$ and extending the $\mathcal{A}_0$ to be $\mathcal{A}_0: L^2(\Omega) \rightarrow [\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A}_0)]'$, we can rewrite (4) as

$$y_{tt}(\cdot, t) = -\mathcal{A}_0 y(\cdot, t) + \mathcal{A}_0 N_1 Lz(\cdot, t) - \mathcal{A}_0 N_2 Lz(\cdot, t) + \mathcal{A}_0 N_2 u(\cdot, t) \in [\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A}_0)]'. \quad (2.2)$$

Thus we can write the system (1.1a-1.1f) as a standard form of linear infinite-dimensional system

$$\text{in } \mathcal{H} \quad Y(t) = \mathcal{A}Y(t) + Bu \quad (2.3)$$

Where

$$Y(t) = \begin{bmatrix} y(\cdot, t) \\ y_t(\cdot, t) \\ z(\cdot, t, s) \end{bmatrix}, \quad z(\cdot, t, s) = y(x, t) - y(x, t - s),$$

$$\mathcal{A} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & I & 0 \\ -\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_0 & 0 & \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_0 N_1 L - \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_0 N_2 L \\ 0 & I & -\frac{\partial}{\partial s} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A}) = \{Y \in \mathcal{H} \mid \mathcal{A}Y \in \mathcal{H}\}$$

And

$$Bu = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_0 N_2 u \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad B: L^2(\Gamma_1) \rightarrow [\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A}^*)]' \text{ is continuous}$$

Finally, a direct computation gives

$$\begin{aligned} (N_2^* \mathcal{A}_0 f, g)_{L^2(\Gamma_1)} &= (\mathcal{A}_0 f, N_2 g)_{L^2(\Omega)} = (\Delta^2 f, N_2 g)_{L^2(\Omega)} \\ &= \int_{\Omega} f \overline{\Delta^2(N_2 g)} dx - \int_{\Gamma_1} [f \overline{\mathcal{B}_2(N_2 g)} - \partial_v f \overline{\mathcal{B}_1(N_2 g)}] d\Gamma \\ &\quad + \int_{\Gamma_1} [\mathcal{B}_2 f \overline{(N_2 g)} - \mathcal{B}_1 f \overline{\partial_v(N_2 g)}] d\Gamma \\ &= - \int_{\Gamma_1} f \overline{g} d\Gamma, \end{aligned}$$

For all $f \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A}_0)$ and $g \in L^2(\Gamma_1)$. Therefore, $N_2^*(\mathcal{A}_0)f = N_2^* \mathcal{A}_0 f = -f|_{\Gamma_1}$, $f \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A}_0)$. It follows that

$$B^* \begin{bmatrix} w \\ v \\ z \end{bmatrix} = -v|_{\Gamma_1}, \quad \forall \begin{bmatrix} w \\ v \\ z \end{bmatrix} \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A}^*). \quad (2.4)$$

Now, let us consider a feedback control so that the input and output are collocated (Ref.7):

$$u = -kB^*(y, y_t, z)^T = ky_t|_{\Gamma_1}, \quad k \geq 0. \quad (2.5)$$

The closed-loop system under this output feedback then becomes

$$y_{tt}(x, t) + \Delta^2 y(x, t) = 0, \quad \text{in } \Omega \times \mathbb{R}^+, \quad (2.6a)$$

$$y(x, t) = \partial_v y(x, t) = 0, \quad \text{on } \Gamma_0 \times \mathbb{R}^+, \quad (2.6b)$$

$$\mathcal{B}_1 y(x, t) - \int_0^\infty g'(s) \partial_v [y(x, t) - y(x, t - s)] ds = 0, \quad \text{on } \Gamma_0 \times \mathbb{R}^+, \quad (2.6c)$$

$$\mathcal{B}_2 y(x, t) + \int_0^\infty g'(s) [y(x, t) - y(x, t - s)] ds = ky_t(x, t), \quad \text{on } \Gamma_1 \times \mathbb{R}^+, \quad (2.6d)$$

$$y(x, 0^+) = y_0(x), \quad y_t(x, 0^+) = y_1(x), \quad (2.6e)$$

$$y(x, -s) = \vartheta(x, t). \quad \text{for } 0 < s < \infty, \quad (2.6f)$$

The initial boundary problem (2.6) can be written as an evolutionary equation in $\mathcal{H}$:

$$\dot{Y}(t) = \mathcal{A}Y(t), \quad Y(0) = Y_0$$

Where $Y = (y, y_t, z)$, $Y_0 = (y_0, y_1, y_0 - \vartheta)$ and

$$\mathcal{A} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & I & 0 \\ -\Delta^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & I & -\frac{\partial}{\partial s} \end{bmatrix}$$

With the domain

$$\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A}) = \left\{ (w, v, z) \in \mathcal{H} \left| \begin{array}{l} \Delta^2 w \in L^2(\Omega), v \in W^\infty, z(\cdot) \in H^1(0, \infty; |g'(\cdot)|; H^1(\Gamma_1)), \\ z \\ [\end{array} \right. \right.$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} (o) = 0, [\mathcal{B}_1 w - g'(s) \partial_v z(s) ds]_{\Gamma_1} = 0, \\ \infty \\ \mathcal{B}_2 w + g'(s) z(s) ds]_{\Gamma_1} = kv|_{\Gamma_1}, \\ 0 \end{aligned} \right\}$$

Where

$$H^1(0, \infty; |g'(\cdot)|; H^1(\Gamma_1)) = \{z(s) \in Z \mid \frac{\partial}{\partial s} z(s) \in Z\}.$$

The following theorem ensures that the system (2.6) is well-posed in $\mathcal{H}$.

Theorem 2.1. Assume that the function g satisfies (g1) through (g3) and $k \geq 0$. Then the operator $\mathcal{A}$ generates a C_0 -semigroup $S(t)$ of contraction on $\mathcal{H}$.

Proof. We first prove that $\mathcal{R}(I - \mathcal{A}) = \mathcal{H}$. Namely, we need to show that the following system of the equations

$$w - v = f, \quad (2.7a)$$

$$v + \Delta^2 w = g, \quad (2.7b)$$

$$z(s) - v + \frac{\partial}{\partial s} z(s) = h(s) \quad (2.7c) \text{ has a solution } (u, v, z) \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A}) \text{ for every } (f, g, \square) \in \mathcal{H}. \text{ In fact,}$$

it follows from (2.6) that

$$v = w - f \in W, \quad (2.8a)$$

$$w + \Delta^2 w = f + g \in L^2(\Omega), \quad (2.8b)$$

$$z(s) = (1 - e^{-s})w + (1 - e^{-s})f + \int_0^\infty e^{\tau-s} \square(\tau) d\tau \in Z. \quad (2.8c)$$

Therefore, $v \in W$ and $z(\cdot) \in H^1(0, \infty; |g'(\cdot)|; H^1(\Gamma_1)), z(0) = 0$.

Furthermore, by (11b)-(11c) we

have that for any

$w \in W$ satisfying $\Delta^2 w \in L^2(\Omega)$ and $\mathcal{B}_1 w - \int_0^\infty g'(s) \partial_v z(s) ds = 0, \mathcal{B}_2 w + \int_0^\infty g'(s) z(s) ds = kv$, it has for all $\phi \in W$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_\Omega w \bar{\phi} dx + a(w, \phi) + \int_{\Gamma_1} [(kw + Xw) \bar{\phi} + X \partial_v w \bar{\phi}] d\Gamma \\ = & \int_\Omega (f + g) \bar{\phi} dx + \int_{\Gamma_1} [(kf + Xf + \Psi) \bar{\phi}] d\Gamma \end{aligned} \quad (2.9)$$

Where

$$X = - \int_0^\infty g'(s)(1 - e^{-s}) ds \geq 0$$

And

$$\Psi = \int_0^\infty g'(s) \int_0^s e^{\tau-s} h(\tau) d\tau ds.$$

We see from the Lax-Milgram theorem (Ref.8) that the equation (2.9) admits a unique solution $w \in W$. Combining this with (2.8a) and (2.8c), we see that $(w, v, z) \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A})$ solves the equation $(I - \mathcal{A})(w, v, z) =$

$(f, g, \square)$.

Next, for any $Y = (w, v, z) \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A})$, it has

$$\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{A}Y) = Y$$

$$= -k \int_{\Gamma_1} |v|^2 d\Gamma - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^\infty \int_{\Gamma_1} g^n(s) (|z(s)|^2 + |\partial_\nu z(s)|^2) d\Gamma ds \leq 0 \quad (2.10)$$

Hence $\mathcal{A}$ is dissipative. We see from the theorem 1.4.6 of Ref.8 that $\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A})$ is dense in $\mathcal{H}$. Therefore, we can conclude by Lumer-Phillips theorem that $\mathcal{A}$ generates a C_0 -semigroup of contractions on $\mathcal{H}$. The proof of Theorem 2.1 is complete now. $\square$

3 A Variable Structural Control for the System

Let us establish a sliding model control for the system (??)

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial Y}{\partial t} = \mathcal{A}Y + Bw(Y, t) \\ Y(0) = Y_0 \end{cases} \quad (3.1)$$

Where B is a bounded linear operator from $\mathcal{H}$ to $\mathcal{H}$, $w(Y, t)$ is the control of the system (3.1) that is not continuous on the manifold $S = CY = 0$, and C is a bounded linear operator with $S = S(Y) = CY \in R^n$.

Now, we consider the δ -neighborhood of sliding mode $S = CY = 0$, where $\delta > 0$ is an arbitrary given positive number. Using a continuous control $w(z, t)$ to replace $w(Y, t)$ in the system 3.1 yields

$$\begin{cases} \dot{Y} = \mathcal{A}Y + B\tilde{w}(Y, t) \\ Y(0) = Y_0 \end{cases} \quad (3.2)$$

where $Y = \partial Y / \partial t$, and the solution of (3.2) belongs to the boundary layer $\|S(Y)\| \leq \delta$

Let $S(Y) = CY = 0$. Applying C to the first equation of (3.1) leads to the following the equivalent control: $w_{eq}(Y, t) = -(CB)^{-1}C(\mathcal{A}Y)$

With assumption that $(CB)^{-1}$ exists. Substitute $w_{eq}(Y, t)$ into 3.1 to find

$$Y = [I - B(CB)^{-1}C]\mathcal{A}Y. \quad (3.3)$$

Denote $P = B(CB)^{-1}C$ and $\mathcal{A}_0 = (I - P)\mathcal{A}$, then 3.1 becomes

$$Y' = \mathcal{A}_0 Y \quad Y(0) = Y_0 \quad (3.4)$$

In the rest part of this paper, we are going to show that the actual sliding mode $Z(Y)$ will approach uniformly to the ideal sliding mode $Z(Y)$ under certain conditions.

Lemma 3.1 If $(CB)^{-1}$ is a compact operator and $P\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{A}P$, then $\mathcal{A}_0 = (I - P)\mathcal{A}$ generates a C_0 -Semigroup $T_2(t)$ in $\mathcal{H}$ and $T_2(t) = (I - p)T_1(t)$, where $T_1(t)$ is the C_0 -semigroup generated by $\mathcal{A}$.

Proof. Since $(CB)^{-1}$ is a compact operator, B and C are bounded linear operators, we see from the definition of P that P is compact, and therefor the range of $I - P$ is a closed subspace of $\mathcal{H}$. Since $P^2 = P$ and $(1 - P)^2 = I - P$, $I - P$ can be viewed as the identity operator on $(I - P)\mathcal{H}$. It can be easily seen that $T_2(t) = (I - P)T_1(t)$ is a C_0 -semigroup in $(I - P)\mathcal{H}$.

Next, we shall prove that the infinitesimal generator of $T_2(t)$ is $(I - P)\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{D}((I - P)\mathcal{A}) = (I - P)\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A})$. In fact, for every $x \in (I - P)\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A})$, there is a $x_1 \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A})$ such that $x = (I - P)x_1$. It should be noted that $T_1(t)$ and $I - P$ are commutative because $\mathcal{A}$ and P are commutative. We see that

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{T_2(t)x - x}{t} &= \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{(I - P)T_1(t)(I - P)x_1 - (I - P)x_1}{t} \\ &= \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{(I - P)^2 T_1(t)x_1 - (I - P)x_1}{t} \\ &= \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{(I - P)T_1(t)x_1 - (I - P)x_1}{t} \\ &= (I - P) \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{T_1(t)x_1 - x_1}{t} \\ &= (I - P)\mathcal{A}x_1. \end{aligned}$$

Let $\mathcal{A}$ be the infinitesimal generator of $T_2(t)$. Since the limit on the left exists, we can assert that $x \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A})$ and $(I - P)\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A})$.

On the other hand, for any $x \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A})$, since $\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq (I - P)\mathcal{H}$, there exists $x \in \mathcal{H}$, such that $x = (I - P)x$, and

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{x - x}{t} &= \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{(I - P)T_1(t)\tilde{x} - (I - P)\tilde{x}}{t} \\ &= \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{T_1(t)\tilde{x} - \tilde{x}}{t} \\ &= (I - P) \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{T_1(t)\tilde{x} - \tilde{x}}{t} \\ &= (I - P)\mathcal{A}\tilde{x}. \end{aligned}$$

Since the limit of the left hand side exists, and so the limit of the right hand side exists, and $x \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A})$ which implies that $\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq (I - P)\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A})$. Thus, $\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A}) = (I - P)\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A})$ and $\mathcal{A}$, the infinitesimal generator of $T_2(t)$, is $(I - P)\mathcal{A}$.

The proof of the lemma is complete.

Theorem 3.2 Suppose that in the system 3.1,

1. $(CB)^{-1}$ exists and it is compact, 2.

$P\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{A}P$, where $P = B(CB)^{-1}C$.

Then for any solution $Y(t)$ of the system 3.4 satisfying $S(\bar{Y}_0) = 0$, $\bar{Y}_0 \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A}_0)$ and $\|Y_0 - \bar{Y}_0\| \leq \delta$, $Y_0 \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A})$, we have

$$\lim_{\delta \rightarrow 0} \|z(t) - \bar{z}(t)\| = 0$$

Uniformly on $[0, T]$ for any positive number T .

Proof. We see from the Theorem 2.1 and Lemma 3.1 that $\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{A}_0 = (I - P)\mathcal{A}$ are infinitesimal generators of C_0 -semigroups $T_1(t)$ and $T_2(t)$ respectively. It follows from theory of semi group of linear operators that there are positive constants M_1, M_2, ω_1 and ω_2 such that

$$\|T_1(t)\| \leq M_1 e^{\omega_1 t}, \quad \|T_2(t)\| \leq M_2 e^{\omega_2 t}. \quad (0 \leq t \leq T) \quad (3.5)$$

In the boundary layer $\|T_1(t)\| \leq \delta$, the equivalent control is

$$w_{eq}(Y, t) = -(CB)^{-1}C\mathcal{A}Y + (CB)^{-1}CY \quad (3.6)$$

Substitute (3.6) into (3.1) to find

$$Y = (I - P)\mathcal{A}Y + PY \quad (3.7)$$

Hence, the solution of (3.7) can be expressed as follows:

$$Y(t) = T_2(t)Y_0 + \int_0^t T_2(t-s)P\dot{Y}(s)ds, \quad (3.8)$$

And the solution of (3.4) can be written as

$$\bar{Y}(t) = T_2(t)\bar{Y}_0 \quad (3.9)$$

Subtracting (3.9) from (3.8) yields

$$Y(t) - \bar{Y}(t) = T_2(t)(Y_0 - \bar{Y}_0) + \int_0^t T_2(t-s)P\dot{Y}(s)ds \quad (3.10)$$

Since $P\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{A}P$, we see that $PT_1(t) = T_1(t)P$. It should be emphasized that $(I - P)P = 0$ and $T_2(t) = (I - P)T_1(t)$, and consequently,

$$\int_0^t (t-s)P\dot{Y}(s)ds = \int_0^t (I - P)T_1(t-s)P\dot{Y}(s)ds$$

$$\int_0^t T_1(t-s)(I - P)P\dot{Y}(s)ds$$

T_2

0

$=$

$0 = 0$

It can be obtained from (3.10) and (3.5) that

$$\| Y(t) - \bar{Y}(t) \| \leq \| T_2(t) \| \| Y_0 - \bar{Y}_0 \| \leq M_2 e^{\omega_2 T} \| Y_0 - \bar{Y}_0 \|,$$

Since $\| Y_0 - \bar{Y}_0 \| \leq \delta$, we have

$$\| Y(t) - \bar{Y}(t) \| \leq M_2 e^{\omega_2 T} \delta.$$

$$\lim_{\delta \rightarrow 0} \| Y(t) - \bar{Y}_0 \| = 0.$$

Thus,

The proof of the theorem is complete.

We see from the Theorem 3.2 that the actual sliding mode can be approximated by ideal sliding mode in any accuracy.

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